

QUALITY ASPECTS OF AND THREAD SELECTION FOR STITCHED PREFORMS

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SUMMARY

Influence of various sewing parameters on the preform quality, manufacturing processes, and composite laminate quality and properties are investigated. Prerequisites of the sewing thread are described according to their significance in the composite processing. As a result, ways to improve the preform and composite quality are illustrated.

Keywords: Preform, sewing, threads, composite, quality

INTRODUCTION

Sewing technique has been implemented for more than two decades to provide through-the-thickness (TTT) reinforcement in composite structures and emerged as one of the important techniques to design textile preforms. As a next step, to improve the mechanical properties, tests on the three-dimensional (3-D) reinforcement at textile fabric and prepreg were also performed [1, 2]. It has also been proved that, the typical laminate properties can be improved by means of appropriate structural sewing [3-5].

Sewing provides a mechanical connection between the preform elements before the resin is introduced, allowing the completed preform to be handled without shifting or damage. In addition, sewing compresses the fiber preform closer to the final desired thickness. Less mechanical compression need then to be applied to the preform in the tool. Furthermore, textile assembling is advantageous in terms of ready to dispatch products with reduced cycle time and cost [6]. Thus, assembling of textile reinforcements to net-shape geometry is a functional aspect of preform sewing. Nevertheless, implementation of the sewing technology for assembling textile structures is introduced quite late [6].

Philosophy of Sewn Preforms for Resin Transfer Molding Technology

Although sewing of 2-D preforms normally adds at least one extra process step, it assists much during the manufacture of laminates based on the resin transfer molding (RTM) technology.

As shown in Figure 1, sewing of different preforms, cutting them to the required contours, and their assembly are the basic stages before the RTM processes. Net-shape preforms are essential for the efficient and fault free RTM processing and sewn preform philosophy offers advantages of such a manufacturing process.

The sewing process becomes effective as a further step in the process chain, immediately after the actual manufacture of the semi-finished fiber product [7]. Nevertheless, it is generally considered damaging to the in-plane properties and deteriorating laminate quality to certain extent, despite the improved out-of-plane properties. Waviness in the fiber material, as a result of the needle penetration, has a negative effect on the in-plane properties of the stitched material. For this reason, a basis must be created in which the sewing process is included as a quantifying and reproducible process of the design of an actual component.

Figure 1: Process flow of stitched composite parts

Sewing Threads for Preform Manufacturing

The sewn preform based on FRPC laminate performance depends on the quality of seam structure and seam efficiency. Sewing threads are also important in the manufacturing of net-shape preforms and LCM processes. The seam efficiency is influenced primarily by the type and quality of the sewing thread used in preform sewing. Apart from this, there are number of factors which affect the FRPC structure and the majority of them are shown in Figure 2. The selection of sewing thread for preforming is based on its physical properties and application areas. Gathered data, based on the experience, for selection of sewing thread used in particular seams is given in Table 1.

In this section, detailed studies on essential properties of sewing threads and their effect on preforming are discussed. Selection of sewing thread based on the preforming applications, thread properties, and suitability for sewing machines are explained in detail.

Preform manufacturing using sewing threads possess numerous challenges such as frequent thread breakages, poor knot formation due to thread snarling, widened stitch-holes, etc. Furthermore, improper selection of thread may affect the microstructure of a laminate, for instance, void formation due to degassing of thread finish, and properties of the laminates. Various studies reported in the literature and some preliminary experiments performed at IVW show that sewing process can be optimized by selecting proper sewing parameters [8]. The basic properties that a sewing thread should possess are discussed in detail in the following section.

Figure 2: Thread properties influencing the FRPC quality

Table 1: Applicability of threads

Stitch type	Seam type	Thread applicable
Modified lock stitch	Fixing and positioning	Thin, flexible, high elongation polyester
	Assembling	Thicker polyester, Nomex [®] , or Kevlar [®]
	Structural (3-D)	Carbon, glass, Kevlar [®]
Chain stitch	Fixing and positioning	Medium thick, less elongation polyester
	Assembling	Thick, less elongation polyester, Kevlar [®]
One-sided stitch	Assembling	Thick polyester
	Structural (3-D)	Carbon, glass, Kevlar [®]
Blind	Fixing and positioning	Medium thick polyester
	Assembling	Polyester, Nomex [®] , or Kevlar [®]
Tufting	Assembling	Polyester, Kevlar [®] , glass
	Structural(3-D)	Carbon, glass, Kevlar [®]

QUALITY EVALUATION OF PREFORMS AND COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Incorporation of sewing thread in the third dimension of reinforcing material is a base of transverse sewing. The associated parameters of sewing process and caused effects are the criteria for evaluating preform quality and later the FRPC quality. The content of this chapter is focused on the analysis of micrographs of stitched (modified lock stitch) preforms as well as laminates to investigate the disturbance caused at in-plane fiber orientation and the geometrical extension of the ellipse formation by the sewing process. Laminate surface imperfections due to matrix shrinkage at ellipse, change in fiber volume at localized sections, and imperfections inside the laminate are

investigated. Furthermore, approaches to improve preform and laminate quality is also discussed.

Formation of Ellipse

The sewing process causes spreading of the reinforcing fibers during the needle penetration, which forms a fiber-free contour over the surface and inside the preform structure. The contour size is based on the position of the sewing thread and is assumed as an ellipse shape for calculation purpose. The fabric lay-up structure, thread variables, and machine parameters define the area of this ellipse. Figure 3 shows theoretical and actual ellipse geometries.

Figure 3: Ellipse geometries considered for calculations

The first theoretical ellipse values can be calculated by measuring minor and major axis of fiber-spread region and then multiplying factor of fiber-spread (0.65) a near real ellipse area can be calculated [9].

Figure 3 also shows micrographs of a sewn woven fabric preform and a composite laminate at stitched section (top view). The polyester thread position at the scanned image of preform and the laminate are also visible in the figure. The micrograph of the laminate clearly shows the typical minor axis (2b) and the major axis of the ellipse (2a). Formation of ellipse in the laminate is completely dependant on fabric geometry, sewing thread geometry, thread tension, and laminate thickness.

Textile material lay-up: For the manufacturing of composite laminates, textile material needs to be positioned in a specific orientation. The ellipse formation and fiber disorder in each layer are observed in the direction of the reinforcing fibers which is again independent of stitch direction

Influence of stitch type: During the sewing operation, though the needle and bobbin thread tensions are adjusted for modified lock stitch, due to the irregularities in sewing thread, irregular friction between fabric and thread, and excessive machine speed, the absolute needle thread tension may fluctuate. This phenomenon of varied thread tension may leads to formation of standard lock stitch geometry. It means that the needle thread pulls the bobbin thread from 1/10th to 1/2 of the laminate depending on the overall laminate thickness. In lock stitch, due to the knot inside the laminate, intensity of ellipse formation and ellipse dimension at the particular layer may also alter. Thus, apart from fiber discontinuity at upper layer, the bottom layer of the laminate may also creates

discontinuity in the reinforcement structure. Generally, in the ideal modified lock stitch, the top surface of the laminate (needle penetration surface) is highly affected in terms of fiber distortion, whereas, theoretically, the bottom surface does not show any sign of fiber distortion. But, in lock stitch or actual modified lock stitch, pulled-in bobbin thread destructs the bottom layers of the laminate [9].

Influence of thread packing: As stated earlier, thread geometry affects the stitch performance and it has been observed that the ellipse areas formed by different threads have different dimensions. Again, due to applied forces on the sewn preform, during the LCM processing the thread packing can change, which causes change in the ellipse shape and dimensions. Densely packed thread leaves small ellipse behind whereas randomly oriented thread causes higher fiber-spread. Thread packing depends on the thread geometry, which includes twist, bulk, number of filaments in the cross-section, etc. Neither soft twisted (soft packed) nor hard twisted threads are recommended for the development of stitched preforms.

Laminate imperfections

In terms of ellipse, fiber-spread may occur during the sewing of preforms which leads to formation of fiber free zones. Various laminate imperfections due to stitches and fiber spreading are explained below.

After the resin injection there are chances of resin accumulation at these zones. Depending on the type of resin system used, shrinkage of this accumulated resin can occur. This phenomenon may cause an uneven laminate surface or micro-cracking. Furthermore this region may cause stress concentration under mechanical load. These types of shortcoming can be avoided by reducing the ellipse formation which will be explained later in this paper.

Fiber volume fraction level at the localized section varies from zero to maximum due to ellipse formation. The maximum volume fraction can be reached up to 70 %. This effect totally depends on the thread specifications and machine parameters. Difference in the fiber volume content may affect the micro structural and mechanical properties. Figure 4 shows a sewn preform and laminate with different localized fiber volume content. Due to the accumulation of fibers under the sewing thread, a relatively thicker section may form. This may create difficulties in mold closure during close mold RTM process and uneven laminate surface in vacuum assisted RTM processed laminate. Apart from this, due to high localized fiber volume, fiber impregnation in this zone is quite complex.

At the stitched section, there are the commonly faced challenges viz. voids and un-impregnated sewing thread. The cause of void formation is generally the degassing of applied chemicals and its incompatibility to the matrix system. By applying a proper thread finish, reduction in voids and proper thread impregnation can be accomplished.

Applied spin-finish or sizing on the sewing thread is a major role playing factor in void formation and poor impregnation of thread. The silicon oil based sizing used for the standard polyester thread contains up to 4 % of oligomers. This hinders the impregnation of polyester thread and application of heat during the curing cycle, degassing of this substance may result the void formation. The phenomenon of void

formation is not only restricted to the laminate surface but it extends around the stitch, inside the laminate.

Due to the penetration of the sewing needle twice at the same location (depends on the type of sewing pattern), the widening of the stitch-hole may be possible. This may cause through-the-thickness resin rich area at the particular section. Figure 4 also shows single and double penetration of needle and formed stitch. This causes an enlarged resin rich area due to the excess thread content at the localized zone and further voids formation or un-impregnated thread.

Figure 4: Localized fiber volume content and laminate micrographs at stitch positions

Another common error observed during the sewing process is missing stitches. Small stitch length and high machine speed causes poor inter-loopment of the thread at the bobbin gripper. As an effect, the needle penetrates through the reinforcing fabric and comes out without any stitch formation. Figure 5a shows a micrograph of the location of a missing stitch. Here, the programmed stitch length was 2.5 mm but due to the missing stitch, the actual stitch length was measured to be 5 mm (2 x set stitch length). Subsequently, due to blank needle penetration, the split in the fiber bundle is a common effect of such phenomenon.

The sewing action disturbs the orientation of the reinforcing fibers, this may result in inter and intra-layer fiber misalignment. Figure 5b shows a NCF laminate with misplaced and disoriented fibers which may lead to poor mechanical performance of the laminate. Proper combination of stitch length, material thickness, and adjustment of machine speed can help to reduce the fiber distortion significantly.

Figure 5: a) missing stitch, b) fiber misplacement due to false stitch

Approaches to reduce imperfections

Imperfections like ellipse formation and related side effects such as void formation, poor fiber impregnation, resin richness, etc. can be reduced to a certain extent by using various methods. This includes chemical treatment of thread, adjustments of sewing machine parameters, selection of sewing thread, etc.

The use of definite sewing threads for a specific delicate reinforcing fiber structure is obligatory and it has been explained in the previous chapter. Judicious utilization of specialty and commodity textile threads can help to reduce sewing imperfections in the subsequent operations.

The compaction of preforms is subject to applied pressure during the RTM processing. During this compression, preform thickness tends to reduce and rearrangement of reinforcing fiber takes place. Apart from this, stitch geometry may change according to the used thread and machine parameters and change in ellipse size can happen.

During the sewing process, low to medium thread tension exerts less force on the preform that results in reduction of fiber distortion. This causes lower ellipse size compared to high thread tension. This leads to easy reorientation of reinforced fibers during the resin impregnation process, which reduces the stitch-hole size. 50 % lower thread tension helps to reduce 60 % of the ellipse size. On the contrary, higher thread tension causes not only in-plane but also out-of-plane irreversible distortion.

For proper impregnation of polyester thread and manufacturing of void-free laminates, the applied thread sizing must be removed. By means of chemical treatments, oligomeric substances shall be washed out from the thread [9] and additional sizing should be applied on the thread, which makes it again sewable. Additional sizing is a prerequisite for a better sewing effect; otherwise, thread could be rough, poor antistatic, and abrasive. Thermally stable (or stabilized) sizing can be the best suitable for sewing and in terms of better laminate quality (no voids and completely impregnated polyester thread).

PREFORM COMPACTION

Preform compaction in the mold is a very critical factor because reinforcing material has to be compressed to achieve the required final thickness of the component. If the preform is too thin, skin-tracking appears [10], which leads to the defective surfaces. However, net-shape preforms are almost impossible to accomplish by using non-compacted preform packages. A partial compaction possibility of semi-finished product is a must in order to achieve proper tool loading and net-shape potential. On the other hand, preforms should be flexible enough wherever it is desired.

Textile woven fabrics consist of wavy warp and weft elements. On the application of compaction force, the crimp in the warp and weft keeps reducing to the jamming condition. As the crimp reduces, the effective fabric dimensions increase, it means the fabric deforms to a certain extent. If fabric boundaries are fixed partially or completely, the lateral deformation of the textile fabric can be restricted and jamming condition occurs much earlier. Preform stitches work in the same fashion, furthermore, the amount textile fabric comes under these stitch boundaries can differ according to the stitch pattern.

Low stitch density reduces the overall weight of preform whereas high stitch density increases the effective weight of the preform and so the fiber volume content. Due to the pre-compaction after stitching, preforms stitched with high stitch density shows relatively higher fiber volume at very less compaction pressure than preforms stitched with low stitch density.

Figure 6 shows intensity of reduction in ellipse size after the application of compaction pressure on the preforms (compaction pressure applied to achieve approximately 65 % fiber volume content).

Low stitch density allows deforming of the preform to a small extent. This reduces the further chances of fluid matrix race-tracking. Whereas, high stitch density does not allow any deformation, which characterizes it for the net-shape preform with pre-defined fiber volume. Consequently, the total fabric deformation due to sewing is negligible. The phenomenon reduction in the stitch-hole size improves the preform quality.

Figure 6: Influence of preform compaction on stitch hole closing

ANALYSIS OF LAMINATES MADE OF SEWN PREFORMS

In this section, an experimental work for qualitative and quantitative analysis of sewn preforms and the laminates made thereof is outlined. Tests were performed to observe influence of sewing parameters on the physical properties of the laminate.

The experiments were designed to analyze the performance of different polyester sewing threads in the FRPC laminate. The test panels used were manufactured from 5-harness (5H) satin fabric (areal weight 370 g/m²). For sewing purpose, four different threads were used A) epoxy compatible twisted multifilaments (23 tex), B) epoxy compatible core spun thread (22 tex), C) untreated textured thread (13 tex), and D) epoxy compatible textured thread (13 tex).

Flat panels with the lay-up construction of [0/90]₄ measuring 220 mm x 180 mm were stitched together. The stitch pattern employed in the specimens was $\pm 45^\circ$ having stitch length of 3 mm and stitch density of 13.33 stitches/cm². Selected cross stitch pattern are generally used for the fixation of preforms with 0°/90° fiber orientation in the fabric structure. The reason behind the selection of dense stitch pattern was to cover a high amount of stitches under the testing zone (e.g. ILS specimen). This method is used to observe the effect of stitches and sewing thread on laminate properties. A modified lock stitch was used to sew the panels.

Unsewn and sewn preform panels were injected with epoxy matrix via vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) process. After the completion of the injection process the composite was cured at 80 °C for 5 h. The manufactured laminate plates were then used for the specimen preparation.

Testing and results

Testing of stitched composite laminates was performed to evaluate the influence of preform sewing. The experimentation was focused on the level of polyester impregnation and its contribution towards the laminate properties. Laminate compression test and interlaminar shear test were performed to investigate the role of joining seams in the composite laminate properties. Though the main aim of these seam types is not through-the-thickness reinforcement, the additional advantage of the seams was investigated through this testing program. 7 specimens per laminate were tested and 5 middle readings were selected for further analysis.

The compression test was performed according to the DIN EN 6036. The Zwick 1485 with compression testing attachments was used for the testing. A loading rate of 0.5 mm/min was used for all specimens. Force required to rupture the specimens was plotted for further analysis.

In Figure 7(L) the comparison between compression strength of stitched and unstitched laminate is indicated. In general, the compressive strength reduces after sewing [11] but in this study the polyester thread with treated epoxy compatible sizing helps to increase the thread matrix bonding. Apart from this, the use of thin polyester thread influences positively the laminate's strength.

Interlaminar shear test (ILS) was performed according to the DIN EN 14125. The data collected from the software was in the form of a plot of bending strength vs. displacement. By using the specifications of each specimen the ILSS values were calculated for all the samples and analyzed. The ILSS calculation was based on the following equation:

$$ILSS = \frac{3 \times P_R}{4 \times t_s \times w_s}$$

where:

$ILSS$ = interlaminar shear strength (MPa), P_R = rupture load (N), w_s = width of specimen (mm), t_s = thickness of specimen (mm)

Due to very short span length of the specimen and high stitch density (27 stitches/specimen area), the micro disturbances in the fiber orientation (caused due to sewing) influences in macro scale.

Figure 74: Comparative (L) Compressive strength, (R) Interlaminar shear stress (ILSS)

Laminates containing thread A and B show lesser stress values but they are more elastic. Laminate stitched with thread C shows more fails at higher stress values and strain values are also more than in the unstitched laminate. Figure 7(R) shows the comparative graph of ILSS values and here, in general the unstitched laminate shows superior performance over the stitched laminates. Nevertheless, it is possible to obtain the ILSS values similar to unstitched specimens by using specific sewing thread (e.g. textured thread).

Microanalysis

To visualize the behavior of ruptured laminates after the tests, specimens were also analyzed at microscopic level. Due to the formed stitch the displacement of the fiber is clearly visible which does affect the bending strength of the laminate as well as the ILSS. The resin rich area at the stitched zone causes the minimization of physical strength of the laminate. Figure 8 shows the micrographs of specimen failed after the compression test and 3PB test respectively. Because of the sewing thread, the laminate failure strength increases slightly and thus the negative effect of the resin rich zone is nullified. In case of short beam shear test (3PB) the crack propagation is restricted because of the crossed thread but it is not enough to negate the influence of fiber disturbances.

Figure 8: Micrograph of failed specimen: after compression (l) and after ILS test (r)

CONCLUSIONS

Various sewing parameters, such as stitch density, stitch pattern, and different stitch formation particulars define the compaction of the fiber package. The compaction behavior of a stitched fabric stack is dominated by fabric architecture. The sewing parameters have to be selected according to the thread used, lay-up of the reinforcing structures, and the type of reinforcing fabric. It can be stated that the combination of high thread tension and higher stitch density or low thread tension and low stitch density have advantage over the unsewn preform. Apart from this, process compatible thread sizing can reduce degassing, bubble formation, and void formation phenomenon.

The results discussed in this paper can help to develop the preforms with improved quality which can enhance composite laminate characteristics and mechanical performance. Preform manufacturing practices and RTM procedures can be improved by selecting appropriate preforming and tool loading parameters. Good quality preforms and composite components can reduce rejections and wastage. Thus, further exploitation of sewing technology for superior composite components is well achievable.

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